

Welcome to the 10th volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

Dear Reader, we wish you a great day and encourage you to read our newsletter. In this volume we wrapping up the Final Symposium and updating you on the progress made by Romania and France. Although our project is coming to an end, we plan to stay in touch with you beyond it's duration.

Let's dive in!

EU-HIP Final Symposium

As the journey of our consortium within the EU-HIP project comes to an end, we had the opportunity to meet one last time in this context. The Final Symposium took place in Copenhagen, Denmark, from March 24 to 26. Over three days, partners from across Europe came together to present the project's key achievements, reflect on lessons learned, and chart a path forward for continued collaboration beyond the life of the joint action.

The Agenda

Day 1

The symposium opened on the 24th of March with welcoming remarks from Pikka Jokelainen (SSI, Denmark) and Han Gysen (DG HERA, Belgium), setting the tone for a reflective yet forward-looking gathering.

The opening session included a Communication and Dissemination update presented by CIPH, Croatia, followed by a presentation of the EU-HIP Baseline Landscape Analysis by THL, Finland — reminding partners of the starting point and scope of the project's work.

After lunch, the afternoon focused on Technical Needs and Interoperability. Norwegian Institute of Public Health led the session, which was followed by a detailed presentation of Work Package 5 (WP5) results by Sciensano, Belgium. This covered needs analyses, roadmaps to implementation, and the progress of national IT systems in meeting interoperability standards. A discussion session allowed partners to exchange views and raise questions.

The day concluded with an interactive session on standards, led by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health and Sciensano.

Day 2

One of the main objectives of this meeting was to give space to representatives of each country to showcase the achievements performed on national level. Thus day 2 started early with the first part of the Key Advancements — Country Presentations, featuring updates from Denmark, Belgium, Croatia, Finland, France, the Netherlands, Germany, and Iceland.

The afternoon opened with two presentations on ATHINA use case results and the European Health Data Space (EHDS) for sustainability. MIN-SAL, Italy and SPMS, Portugal shared results and outlined how the EHDS framework could serve as a vehicle for sustaining the project's outcomes. This was followed by an EHDS Workshop facilitated by MIN-SAL, Italy.

The day closed with a Stakeholder Presentations session, which included contributions from several projects and entities which are closely related in their scope to EU-HIP: JA STOCKPILE, WHO Europe's Head of Data, AI and Digital Health, JAMRAI 2.0 and a preview of the upcoming JA PREPAREDNESS initiative.

Day 3

The final day brought the second part of the Key Advancements — Country Presentations, with updates from Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, and Sweden — completing the picture of EU-HIP's reach and impact across Europe.

Following the country presentations, SPMS, Portugal led an Evaluation session to consolidate feedback and reflections from across the symposium. After lunch, the floor turned to Next Steps, with a discussion on the continuation of cooperation with HERA and the future of ATHINA beyond the project, facilitated by Han Gysen (DG HERA, Belgium) and Jos van Vlerken (SSI, Denmark).

Our journey in this format formally concludes on April 30, but that doesn't mean our work will stop.

In the last three years our consortium has showcased multiple strengths. Partner institutes from multiple countries around Europe have different scopes of work, providing expertise in various fields. When gathered under a common initiative, partners are able to exchange experiences and knowledge in a more structured way, closing the gaps within institutions and enabling more systematic implementations in a shorter time. EU-HIP has also demonstrated the advantage of being a “network of networks” - it can be easy to get lost among all national and international activities which are going on within specific fields in public health and emergency preparedness. Having multiple viewpoints enables us to filter out the most advanced projects with the expected outcomes of interest.

As a consortium, EU-HIP will continue its work with the aim to preserve connections and interactions among partners and stakeholders outside of the consortium. We have already kicked-off **Monthly Alignment Meetings with HERA** which will serve as a framework to keep the communication channels alive and enable timely responses to future initiatives.

Progress in Romania and France

Updates from Romania

Romania has used the EU-HIP funding to upgrade the old legacy system and build a new comprehensive National Communicable Diseases Register (NCDR). The upgraded Surveillance System now serves as a centralised platform for collecting and managing epidemiological, laboratory, and hospital data nationwide. Enhancements included system standardisation, improved usability, Docker-based deployment, real-time reporting, and stronger interoperability with national registries. Originally developed for pandemic response, it has evolved into a sustainable, long-term public health infrastructure.

Complementing this, the Transitional Data Validation and Reporting Platform (iRUBT) addresses data quality challenges in legacy systems by enabling validation, error detection, and structured reporting without disrupting ongoing operations. It strengthens data reliability and supports alignment with European surveillance standards.

Next steps include transitioning to a full national register, improving data quality, adopting standards like HL7 FHIR and ICD-11, and aligning with the European Health Data Space.

Romania's experience highlights how crisis-driven innovation can become lasting infrastructure through strategic development and strong institutional collaboration.

Updates from France

France has focused its efforts on two systems: SI-CORRUSS and The Health ETL Platform.

SI-CORRUSS is France's primary platform for managing national health alerts, exceptional health situations, and routine coordination between health authorities.

During EU-HIP, SI-CORRUSS was deeply modernised. New features include a collaborative crisis management module, the introduction of new national reporting processes aligned with the French legal framework, greater flexibility in settings and management, and reinforced responsiveness and security. The system now offers an end-to-end solution — from local event reporting to national crisis management — with automated workflows built around a common nomenclature of health events and data standards.

Running in parallel, the Health ETL Platform was substantially upgraded from its origins as a COVID-19 solution into a full-fledged national interoperability infrastructure. It now incorporates LABOé-SI for notifiable disease data and offers three core functions: pseudonymisation, data quality control, and file transfer across a variety of standards. It acts as a single point for health system data exchanges across France, and is envisioned as the primary interface with the international level — making it a critical component for cross-border collaboration.

**Thank you for
being with us!**

The EU-HIP consortium would like to thank you for your valuable inputs and contributions during the lifespan of our project.

Stay subscribed to our newsletter and social media platforms because we will continue to keep you informed about future initiatives beyond EU-HIP.